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TABLE OF CONTENTS

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	5
Introduction	6
2 Theory of boundary conditions	7
2.1 Formalization	7
2.2 Multipole expansion	9
2.3 Explicit solution for the Spiral phase plate	9
2.4 Strategies of electrode design	10
3 Experiments	11
3.1 Experimental setup	11
3.2 The current divider solution	11
3.3 The realized devices	13
3.4 Experimental images	14
Conclusions	16
Bibliography	16
CONCLUSION	19
ANNEX 2: ABBREVIATIONS	20
Short Name Of Participants	20
List Of Abbreviations	20

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

In this deliverable we report on the realisation, characterisation and improvement of the MEMS device based on the new ideas and technology.

For practical reason we report the measurements in the form of a paper that will be soon submitted as additional form of advertisement for the MINOEN device in the community.

The article shows explicitly the device and uses its branding name giving a clear demonstration of its potentialities.

In particular we demonstrate here the improved control of the boundary conditions including the ohmic path that permit to more smoothly distribute the boundary conditions. This should represent one of the TRL advance of this device.

We also report part of the theory that was initially developed in D2.1 but that has been here further refined.

The section of the deliverable follow the sections of the paper.

Improved electrostatic devices for MEMS-based beam shaping: the spiral phase plate

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Abstract

MEMS based electron optics are a promising approach for a new generation of experiments in electron microscopy. In this contribution we improve analytically the modelling of the MEMS based phase plates with thin electrodes with accurate account of the fringing fields. As a result we are able to improve the design and the boundary conditions in MEMS-based spiral phase plates acting on the control parameters. We checked the quality of the generated vortex beam.

INTRODUCTION

Electron microscopy is undoubtedly one of the most versatile and unique techniques to characterise materials and organic molecules alike. At the basis of this success there is the ability to build lenses and more complicated electron optical systems.

Nowadays optical system can be built to beat the high order geometrical aberration [1–4], the chromatic aberration [5,6], producing magnetic field free atomic resolution [7] and pushing energy resolution [8].

This implies building a large system of lenses considerably contributing to the size and complexity of the microscope.

Yet the upcoming revolution in electron beam control may not come from large optical systems but from the introduction of miniaturised electron optics based on MEMS technology [9,10]. In particular thin Si based chips can be placed in apertures of the microscope and used to affect the phase of a beam.

While nothing can beat the stability and precision of a large magnetic lens, miniaturised electron optics uses magnetic and electric fields generated in a region very close to the beam to produce a more complex phase pattern.

Due to the small distance between the electrodes and the beam, miniaturised optics can produce large phase effects with a small electrical field. However, the most important advantage of miniaturised optics is the flexibility to change the complex phase pattern by just changing the MEMS device.

Recently the demonstration of a new electro optical configuration called “OAM sorter” has been the visible demonstration of the complexity that can be reached by MEMS based optics.

The device combines two MEMS to impart two phase effects to an electron beam, and the collective effect of their combination can be described as the conformal mapping of the electron wavefunction. The device has allowed for the first time the direct measurement of the spectrum of orbital angular momentum components of a beam. Beyond the OAM sorter even more complex conformal mapping have been predicted and would be useful to improve the measurements possibilities.

The counterpart of this complexity is the necessity to introduce also an artificial intelligence control of such optics that will allow to align complex and imperfect optical systems with many bias voltages and to integrate it in the microscope operations [11].

The success of this approach may lead us to think that in principle we can produce very complex and arbitrary phase landscapes, but the reality is that in most real cases we suffer from many limitations.

As described in ref [9] the MEMS electron optics is based on very thin lenses and under most circumstances (for example with well-behaved boundary conditions and charge neutrality see appendix 1) can introduce only “harmonic” phase effects to the electron beam. Harmonic means that $\nabla_{xy}^2\varphi = 0$ where x,y are the in-plane coordinates orthogonal to the main propagation direction z. This is due to the fact that we don’t want electrodes directly illuminated by the electron beams as this would come with charging and fast ageing of the device. However, we still tolerate minor deviations from this rule by allowing a few electrodes along the electron path. Assuming that the size of these elements is small compared to the beam size we can still speak about “quasi-harmonic” phase plates.

This kind of phase is still relevant both because harmonic phase plates are exactly those that control the conformal transformation of the wavefunction [12] and because single harmonic phase plates can be used for the generation of interesting waves. One of these is the spiral phase plate that permits to generate electron vortex beams but can be used also as a post-specimen filter for diffracted electrons in order to enhance the edge contrast. [13]

The device has been already realised in the past magnetically and electrostatically but with some limitations. [14,15]

However, the realisation of a working spiral phase plate is used to demonstrate an improvement of the MEMS technology (the special MEMS devices are hereafter referred to as “MINEON” MINIaturised Electron Optics for Nanobeams) and in the electrostatic modelling. In particular we work here on the realisation of the best control so far of boundary conditions that ensure an improvement of the quality of the vortex beam with different quanta of angular momentum with minimal distortion.

2 THEORY OF BOUNDARY CONDITIONS

2.1 Formalization

We will explore here the mathematical description of the effect of a planar set of thin electrodes delimiting the area of the beam. The finite but limited size of the electrodes requires the necessity to correctly describe the 3D field or what for a lens could be called the fringing fields

This will be a fundamental theoretical framework necessary to fix the electrode bias and geometry for the boundary conditions. Due to the very high energy of the electron all the phase problem is bi-dimensional and given by the projection of the electrostatic problem of the potential generated by charges.

The phase of a set of fixed charges satisfies the equation [16]:

$$\nabla_{xy}^2\varphi = \sigma \quad [1]$$

Where σ is the projected charge. So $\sigma \neq 0$ only on materials that are introduced in the electron beam. In real experiments we would prefer as much as possible to reduce the amount of material along the beam path so we typically have a “hole” region surrounded by planar electrodes. This constraint can be somehow relaxed without loss of generality by allowing small lines of charge to be inserted in the “hole” region.

The phase is related to the potential by the equation $\varphi = C_E \int Vdz$ where C_E is the appropriate constant [17].

As it can be seen, this problem is apparently the analogue of the electrostatic problem in 3D.

The solution of eq. 1 for a given set of fixed charges is quite simple but in the real world we face a more complex problem where the phase is determined by electrodes that do not have a fixed charge which are indeed defined by the solution of a full 3D electrostatic problem.

Fig. 1 Connection between the 3D electrostatic problem and the phase.

The Dirichlet problem for the potential V is well defined by

$$\{\nabla^2 V = 0 \mid V|_{\partial\Omega} = v(s)\} \quad [2]$$

Where $v(s)$ is the planar potential distribution on electrodes with surface coordinates described by $s \in \partial\Omega$. If we could write the analogy for the phase we would write

$$\{\nabla^2 \varphi = 0 \mid \varphi|_{\partial\Sigma} = f(x, y)\} \quad [3]$$

But in the general case we don't know the phase effect at a given boundary x, y position because it depends on the full 3D development of the electrostatic potential.

It is therefore useless in most circumstances to express the problem as in eq. 3. The only significant exception is when the thickness t of the electrodes is very large in comparison to the in-plane extension of the "hole". In such cases the phase boundary condition is written as

$$f(x_s, y_s) \approx C_E v(s(x_s, y_s))t \quad [4]$$

Where x_s, y_s are coordinates on the $\partial\Sigma$ curve. And this can be generally resolved. Such a "thick electrodes" case will be of great importance in the solution of this problem. As opposed we define here a "thin electrode", namely the case where t is comparable or smaller than the size of the hole. This is the typical geometry for MINEON-MEMS devices. As a further simplification, we will assume that the hole is circular. Being $\rho =$

$\sqrt{x^2 + y^2}$, the region of the hole can be described as $\rho < R$ where R is the hole radius. Moreover, we assume that for $\rho > R$ the electrode's shape depends only on the azimuthal coordinate. The advantage of this geometry is that it allows polar variable separation while it is still relevant for many applications.

2.2 Multipole expansion

The consequence of the hole geometry is that the solutions of the “thick electrode” and “thin electrode” solution can be all written as:

$$\varphi_{thin} = \sum_m a_m \rho^m \sin(m\theta + p_m) \quad [5]$$

This is a consequence of the harmonic constraint that in both cases induces a relation between the radial and azimuthal part. The “thick electrode” case will be written hereafter as:

$$\varphi_{thick} = \sum_m A_m \rho^m \sin(m\theta + p_m) \quad [6]$$

Assuming a thick case is like assuming there is no fringing field.

For an aimed phase distribution the coefficient can be easily calculated by the boundary conditions:

$$\varphi_{thick}(\rho = R) = \sum_m A_m R^m \sin(m\theta + p_m) \quad [7]$$

However, in the case of a thick electrode approximation the boundary phase $\varphi_{thick}(\rho = R) = C_E V(\theta, \rho = R)t$ can be related to the applied bias to the boundary electrodes.

For the thin case the problem of finding the relation between phase and applied bias is transformed in the problem of finding the relation between A_m and a_m . However, for this we need to analyse the actual electrostatic solution.

The effect of the fringing field and therefore the relation between the two cases has been extrapolated from literature arguments [18]. We assume in agreement with these results that the thin case is roughly equivalent to the thick case at the condition to substitute the thickness $t \rightarrow t + R/m$.

This means that higher order multipoles have a much shorter fringing field.

The relation between the coefficient is therefore summarised as.

$$a_m \approx A_m \frac{t + \frac{R}{m}}{t} = A_m \left(1 + \frac{R}{mt}\right) \quad [8]$$

This formula is a universal rule on how to create boundary conditions for any case of harmonic phase profile projected on a circular hole. In fact, the phase profile at the frontier of the hole can be predicted from the desired analytical phase expression and the coefficient A_m arises from the Fourier decomposition in the angular basis.

We can therefore pretend to be in the thick case and apply a voltage bias on electrodes:

$$V = \frac{1}{C_E t} \sum_m \frac{A_m}{1 + \frac{R}{mt}} \rho^m \sin(m\theta + p_m) \quad [9]$$

The correction vanishes if m is large or if $t \gg R$ i.e. the thick electrode case. The interpretation is the following: if the desired harmonic phase landscape is described by coefficients a_m the applied bias should have the form of eq. 9. Finally note that the formula for large t reduces indeed to the case of “thick electrodes”.

2.3 Explicit solution for the Spiral phase plate

The spiral phase plate does not directly belong to this scheme since the device is composed of two parts: the chopstick itself and the electrodes on the boundary conditions.

The assumption that we make is that the respective mutual induction between the boundary and the chopstick is negligible so that the two problems can be solved separately.

We will tackle the boundary condition while using the finite element in appendix 2 to join the two solutions. In this case of the boundary conditions of the spiral phase plate with voltage $V(\theta) = k\theta$ the Fourier coefficient

can be given analytically as in polar coordinates the function f is just a linear ramp. In fact, the Fourier series of a sawtooth wave has the analytical form $A_m = 1/m$

That means the actual potentials to be applied have the form:

$$V(\theta) = \frac{1}{c_E t} \sum_m \frac{\varphi_0/m}{1+\frac{mR}{t}} R^m \sin(m\theta + p_m) \quad [10]$$

The result is the green curve showing a strong gradient in proximity of the chopsticks electrodes ($\theta \approx \pm\pi$) and a weaker linear ramp in front of the electrodes.

Fig 2 (blue) Azimuthal distribution voltage on the boundary condition for an ideal spiral phase plate, (yellow) actual phase profile obtained with a thin electrode and (green) actual voltage profile required to obtain a perfect azimuthal phase ramp.

Fig 3 (left) 2D Ideal phase profile for boundary conditions(without the chopstick) phase plate (right) tension at the boundary after the correction

2.4 Strategies of electrode design

Designing this electrode geometry cannot be too easy since only a limited number of electrodes can be addressed.

We can afford the creation of the boundary conditions in two forms:

- 1) **Real space approach:** we can try to match directly the azimuthal shape in real space by appropriately positioning the electrodes along the azimuth.
- 2) **Multipole space approach:** we can start from an ideal azimuthal ramp and decompose the deviation between the ideal and real boundary conditions by adding multipoles of increasing order

The solution 1 is made possible by the fact that the solution is linear in a large portion of the angular range. A linearly decaying potential is now possible with the use of current and resistive paths and will be described better in the experimental section.

The main limit of this approach is that it may be difficult to introduce a strong gradient in the region close to the chopstick.

The solution 2 is explicitly relying on the multipole decomposition that is of general applicability.

It also relies on the fact that a microscope already has means to correct the tilt and the astigmatism that are the first leading terms. What is not included is higher order astigmatism. The partial compensation is therefore obtained by adding a tunable hexapole to the linear azimuthal phase ramp. Additional 4th order effects could be partially added by addressing the 6 electrodes separately, but the combined use of microscope and MEMS control should give enough control over the phase since the further orders are depressed in the $1/m$ series.

In all cases the analytical solution regards only the boundary condition but it is necessary to connect the boundary conditions to the chopstick itself. The boundaries are based on large electrodes while the chopstick electrodes are thin and constructed with juxtaposed opposite polarity. It is safe to assume that the chopstick has nearly no fringing field.

Using qualitatively the same argument as above we can assume that the slowly varying boundary with average V_b potential produce a phase $\varphi = C_E V_b (t + R)$ while the chopstick with potential V_c roughly $\varphi = C_E V_c t$.

It is therefore necessary to introduce a potential in the chopstick much larger than in the boundary. In our case the finite element indicate a $V_c \approx 4 V_b$.

This has been confirmed also by simulations with finite elements shown in the appendix.

3 EXPERIMENTS

3.1 Experimental setup

We positioned the MINEON-MEMS in the sample position of a TEM in the Thermofisher I-V holder that was biased by a computer-controlled bias generator.

The device was then in the TEM by holography and diffraction. For holography we used both a TITAN–HOLO and a THALOS.

The TITAN HOLO microscope equipped with X-FEG, image aberration corrector and two biprims in the projection system. The microscope was operated at 300 Kev and the images were acquired through a Gatan-K2 camera.

The THALOS is operated at 200KeV and has one standard biprism while images are taken using a CETA camera.

For diffraction we used a TITAN –T equipped with image aberration corrector. For the diffraction we used low angle diffraction mode with the objective lens off. In these conditions the Objective aperture is in the same plane as the device. A 30 μm aperture was inserted in such a plane in order to observe the influence of aberration effect and boundary condition but still have a relatively good quality of the beam.

3.2 The current divider solution

As anticipated the bias to be applied is, in many parts of the contour, linearly dependent on the azimuthal coordinates. On the other hand it is difficult experimentally to introduce a voltage gradient in the boundary

conditions. One solution we adopted is to run a current between connected electrodes. Due to the resistance of the circuit the different points of the boundary end up having an intermediate potential between the two external connections, i.e., an electrical potential gradient.

Fig 3 Design of the basic SPP device: the square labyrinths are resistive paths that allow a smooth voltage gradient between two points at the boundary

The figure shows the geometry of one of our devices that contain 4 lateral contacts at 45°, 135°, 225° and 315° plus the two connections to the chopstick.

All electrodes apart from the actual chopsticks are connected together, but the presence of the different contacts at different biases introduces a tension gradient.

The main problem with this approach is that Si is quite heavily doped and the current would be easily very high. It is for this reason that an additional resistive path has been added for a total of 11 “ohmic labyrinths”

that act as discrete resistors. The calculated resistance is of the order of $1 \text{ K}\Omega$

Fig 4 Holography of the mapping of different part of the boundary. The holography shows that a dipole is formed at the border between two electrodes connected by resistive paths.

Fig 4 shows the discontinuities in the holography based phase reconstruction in the different areas of the boundary condition. In this case we used a chopstick bias of $\pm 4 \text{ V}$: due to the discreteness of the resistors at each discontinuity a change of potential of the order of 0.5 V is produced and a phase of roughly 4π .

3.3 The realised devices

Consistently with the theoretical section we realised 3 different philosophies of device. In addition to the basic design in figure 3, a few additional designs have been produced and are shown in figure 5. They are also potential alternatives based on the two principles **real space and multipole approach**.

Fig 5 Alternative designs of boundary conditions for the chopstick

In figure 5 the device on the left is based on a real space approach and in particular on putting contacts only on the side of the chopstick. The azimuthal gradient of the phase on the front part is therefore taken care only by the current and the smooth resistive loss of potential.

The device on the right is based on the explicit hexapole control and it features the 6 contacts equally spaced on the azimuthal directions where one of the poles is the chopstick itself.

The hexapole is explicitly oriented along the chopstick and this implies that not both hexapoles directions are necessary as it would be necessary for a generic 3-fold astigmatism. Both these devices have not been actually used in these tests but they will be analysed and used in future works.

3.4 Experimental images

For the testing of the device we wrote a specialised software that simplifies the 8 bias to 4 main parameters that are summarised here.

M=main bias on the single chopstick

O=offset additional bias to compensate chopstick asymmetry

F=factor defining the relation from the chopstick to boundary conditions

S=overshoot additional correction for the thin electrodes case

B=M x F scale factor of the boundary condition

The relation of these parameters to the applied bias is visible in table 1.

electrode	Formula vs parameters
V1	-M +O
V2	-0.5 B
V3	$(-0.5+1/11) \times (S+B)$
V4	$(-0.5+4/11) \times (S+B)$

V5	$(-0.5+7/11)x(S+B)$
V6	$(-0.5+10/11)x(S+B)$
V7	0.5 B
V8	M +O

We therefore investigated the effect of each parameter of the overall vortex shape.

Fig 6 Test of the effect of the parameter O (offset) on the shape of the vortex. It mainly affects the discontinuity. Other parameters are $M=2V$ $S=-0.3V$, $F=0.8$

Fig 6 illustrates the effect of the offset: by varying this parameter we can take care of the discontinuity occurring as the effect of the finite size of the chopstick. For an ideal condition $O=0$ should give the best vortex shape but we find that an optimal value is obtained for $O=0.1$. This corresponds to a slight asymmetry of the two chopstick electrodes.

Fig 7 Check the effect of the parameter F on the vortex shape. It mainly affects the elongation of the vortex. Other parameters are $M=2V$, $O=0.1V$, $S=-0.3V$

The factor F takes care of the boundary conditions. The ideal value is between $F=0.4$ and 0.8 so we can easily see a deformation for large value of $|F|$. In particular for $F=-2$ we observe a strong elongation of the vortex with one lobe correspondence of the discontinuity. This means that the main axis of the deformation is along the chopstick direction.

In fig 8 we carried out a specific experiment and deformed the vortex by selecting $F=-1$. We then corrected the astigmatism using the stigmation quadrupole of the microscope. The result is the image on the right. The image is clearly affected by 3-fold astigmatism. The 3-fold astigmatism has again its main axis along the chopstick direction.

Fig 8 (left) near-optimal vortex, (center) vortex with an increased value of F (right) the same vortex after correcting the astigmatism in the microscope. Parameters are $M=2V$, $O=0.1V$, $S=-0.3V$

This is in perfect agreement with the prediction of the multipole model that indicate that 1) the boundary condition affect the m-poles series 2) the main correction after the 2-fold astigmatism is the 3-fold astigmatism 3) that only one direction of 3-fold astigmatism (along the chopstick) is needed for the correction.

Finally we show here in fig 9 the result for the parameter S but unfortunately the data do not show a very marked dependency on this factor. S should measure the correction of the boundary condition to account for fringing field and the finite thickness of the electrodes.

The fact that we used the electrodes at $t=30\ \mu\text{m}$ with a radius $R=40\ \mu\text{m}$ means that the fringing field is not so important.

Fig 9

Check of the effect of the S parameter. The effect appears to be a high order correction but still elongating the vortex. Other parameters are $M=2V$, $O=0.1V$, $F=0.8$.

CONCLUSIONS

To conclude we created a general theoretical framework to describe boundary conditions in thin electrostatic lens systems such as those created by MINEON-MEMS. The method is of general interest for MEMS electron optics and uses a multipole decomposition to predict and compensate for the effect of the fringing field. In the case of the spiral phase plate based on “chopstick electrodes” this method allowed, for the first time, to have correct boundary conditions on a spiral phase plate.

This has been verified experimentally in the production of high quality vortex beams but will be essential also when trying to create ideal spiral phase plates for the analysis of dose sensitive materials.

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Appendix 1

In absence of free charges $\nabla^2 V = 0$, we investigate here to which extent we can assume that

$\nabla_{xy}^2 \phi = 0$. The condition $\nabla^2 V = 0$ is equivalent to $\nabla_{xy}^2 V = -\frac{\partial^2 V}{\partial z^2}$.

Therefore when calculating $\nabla_{xy}^2 \phi$ apart from constants is

$$\nabla_{xy}^2 \int V dz = \int \nabla_{xy}^2 V dz = \int -\frac{\partial^2 V}{\partial z^2} dz = -\frac{\partial V}{\partial z} \Big|_{z \rightarrow \infty}$$

In most cases this quantity vanishes because the fields and their derivatives tend to vanish at large distances.

Appendix 2: COMSOL simulation

COMSOL simulations can be used to verify the overall field of the device and also consider the conjunction of the boundary condition with the proper chopstick.

The simulated device here is based on 9 controlled elements as this permits simulating more geometrical effect and different designs. The COMSOL program solves both the electrostatic Dirichlet equation and the Ohmic problem with current so that a near-ideal potential gradient is found on the boundaries.

The result is a 3D potential: we can show here in fig s1 an horizontal and a vertical section of the potential. The value of the potentials in the 9 electrodes is indicated in the table

Tab. 1 Applied biases in the simulations

Electrode	V1	V2	V3	V4	V5	V6	V7	V8	V9
Tension	15	2.2	1.15	0.8	0	-0.8	-1.15	-2.2	-15

Fig s1 The potential is here plotted in a horizontal and vertical section. In the vertical direction the field is strongly concentrated for the chopstick while the electrodes in the boundary extend on larger distances

The table clearly indicates that the potential of the chopsticks in the plane of the electrodes is much stronger than the phase of the boundary conditions. However in the vertical profile we can observe that the potential arising from the boundary condition is much more extended in the vertical direction. In fact the charge compensation between the chopsticks make the chopstick appear as neutral at sufficient distance while the large electrodes of the boundary condition extend for much longer distance.

Fig s2 Phase as integral of the potential in the z direction and sine of the phase. The circle indicates the hole area of the device.

As a result even if the potential in the plane of the electrodes do not appear to be evenly spaced in the azimuthal direction, the phase calculated as the z integral of the potential produces a near-perfect vortex beam.

CONCLUSION

This work demonstrates all the work we have done in terms of improving the TRL and that our device has reached a higher level of reliability and control of the OAM.

These results have also been used to design the electronics and software that are described in the D3.4 cost estimate.

With respect to the previous deliverable 2.2 we have shown that the device is even more precise and this opens the way to more marketable application for example as phase plate for biological applications that is potentially the most interesting application on long term,

ANNEX 1: ABBREVIATIONS

SHORT NAME OF PARTICIPANTS

Partner	Country	Short Name
1 CONSIGLIO NAZIONALE DELLE RICERCHE	ITALY	CNR
2 QED FILM & STAGE PRODUCTIONS LTD	UNITED KINGDOM	QED
3 THERMO FISHER SCIENTIFIC	THE NETHERLANDS	FEI
4 FORSCHUNGSZENTRUM JÜLICH	GERMANY	FZJ

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Consortium Agreement	CA
Description of Action	DoA
Description of Work	DoW
European Commission	EC
Grant Agreement	GA
Kick-off Meeting	KoM
Project Management Board	PMB
Work Package	WP
Work Package Leader	WPL